

Thin layer chromatography of amino acids on impregnated and unimpregnated silica gel layers developed with water-in-oil microemulsion

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Thin layer chromatographic behavior of twentyfour amino acids has been examined on plain silica gel as well as silica gel layers impregnated with cationic and anionic aqueous solutions using water-in-oil microemulsion as mobile phase. The impregnated plates were stable and gave well-formed spots. Silica gel impregnated with 2% CuSO₄ solution was found most suitable layer material for selective separation of DL-phenylalanine from other amino acids. The limit of detection of some amino acids has also been determined.

Because of its simplicity, rapidity, low cost and excellent resolving power, silica gel thin layer chromatography (tlc) has been extensively used for the separation and identification of amino acids¹⁻³. The selective separation of an analyte on thin layers is generally governed by interactions of the sample molecules with the stationary phase and the coordinative properties of the mobile phase. The composition of the mobile phase is usually altered to achieve the desired separation. As a result, several aqueous, non-aqueous and mixed aqueous organic solvent systems in combination of a variety of stationary phases have been used for chromatographic separation of amino acids. The complex formation tendency of transition metal ions with amino acids as ligands is well documented^{4,5}. Bhushan and Prasad⁶ used silica gel impregnated with transition metal ions for tlc separation of certain amino acids using water-butanol-acetic acid as mobile phase. A chitin-Cu bed developed with mixed aqueous organic solvent system (methanol + propanol + water, 5 : 1 : 4, v/v/v) has been utilized by Malinowska and Rozylo⁷ for the separation of DL-amino acid mixtures.

All these chromatographic studies have been performed using traditional mobile phases as developers and no work has been reported on the use of microemulsion as mobile phase for the separation of amino acids¹. Our studies on tlc separation of anions with water-in-oil microemulsion as mobile phase encouraged us to develop a tlc method for selective separations of amino acids using microemulsion system as mobile phase.

Results and Discussion

Microemulsions are thermodynamically stable mixture containing oil (non-polar solvent), water and often an amphiphilic molecule called co-surfactant. These systems are optically clear because of their much smaller droplet size

(0.01–0.1 mm). A microemulsion is formed when a co-surfactant (medium short-chain alcohol or amine) is added to coarse-emulsion (water-surfactant-oil) up to clarity⁸. In the present study we have used water-in-oil microemulsion consisting of sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), heptane, pentanol and water. The results are summarized in Figs. 1–4 and Tables 1, 2.

Table 1. Selective separation of DL-phenylalanine from other amino acids with water-in-oil microemulsion mobile phase

Stationary phase	Separations achieved (R _F)	
Silica gel impregnation with 2% CuSO ₄ solution	DL-Phenylalanine (0.53)	L-Ornithine monohydrochloride (0.25)
		(0.48) – L-Histidine monohydrochloride (0.25)
		(0.52) – DL-Nor-leucine (0.28)
		(0.50) – DL-Threonine (0.26)
		(0.51) – L-Glutamic acid (0.23)
		(0.47) – L-Lysine monohydrochloride (0.16)
		(0.47) – L-Hydroxyproline (0.07)
		(0.44) – DL-Alanine (0.13)
		(0.53) – L-Proline (0.18)
		(0.54) – DL-Serine (0.29)

Table 2. Detection and dilution limit of amino acids on plain silica gel layer developed with water-in-oil microemulsion

Amino acid	Limit of detection (µg)	Limit of dilution ×10 ⁵
L-Ornithine monohydrochloride	0.04	1 : 2.50
DL-Aspartic acid	0.06	1 : 1.60
L-Cystiene hydrochloride	0.06	1 : 1.60
L-Hydroxyproline	0.05	1 : 20
DL-Alanine	0.09	1 : 1.11
Dilution limit = 1 : Volume of test solution ×10 ⁶ / [limit of detection (µg)].		

Water-in-oil microemulsion produces compact and brighter spots on plain silica gel layers compared to impregnated layers. However, differential migration of amino

Fig. 1. Plots of ΔR_F vs amino acids : (■) $\Delta R_F = R_F$ on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on silica gel impregnated with 2% Ni^{2+} and (▲) $\Delta R_F = R_F$ on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on silica gel impregnated with 2% Zn^{2+} .

Fig. 2. Plots of ΔR_F vs amino acids : (■) $\Delta R_F = R_F$ on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on silica gel impregnated with 2% Fe^{2+} and (▲) $\Delta R_F = R_F$ on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on silica gel impregnated with 2% Cd^{2+} .

Fig. 3. Plots of ΔR_F vs amino acids : (■) $\Delta R_F = R_F$ on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on silica gel impregnated with 2% Cu^{2+} and (▲) $\Delta R_F = R_F$ on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on silica gel impregnated with 2% Hg^{2+} .

acids was observed only on impregnated layer. The development time was 12 min for 10-cm ascent. Figs. 1–4 show that the selectivity of silica gel towards amino acids is altered on impregnation with both cations and anions. At

0.5% impregnant concentration, most of the amino acids produce tailed spots with all impregnants except Li^+ . The magnitude of tailing decreases with the increase in the concentration, leading to the formation of well-formed and

Fig. 4. Plots of ΔR_F vs amino acids : (■) $\Delta R_F = R_F$ on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on silica gel impregnated with 2% Cl^- , (▲) $\Delta R_F = R_F$ on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on silica gel impregnated with 2% Br^- and (●) $\Delta R_F = R_F$ on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on silica gel impregnated with 2% I^- .

compact spots at 2% concentration of the impregnants. Therefore, silica gel impregnated with 2% aqueous solution was selected for detailed study of migration behavior of amino acids.

The results obtained in pure (or plain/unimpregnated) silica gel and silica gel impregnated with 2% metal salts solutions have been compared and the difference in R_F values ($\Delta R_F = R_F$ on unimpregnated silica gel plate $-R_F$ on impregnated silica gel plate) have been plotted (Figs. 1-4). Amino acids producing compact spots ($R_L - R_T < 0.3$) on both unimpregnated and impregnated silica plates, have been taken for drawing the Figs. and the amino acids giving badly tailed spots on either impregnated or unimpregnated plate have been omitted. The positive ΔR_F value (R_F on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on metal ion impregnated silica gel layer) for basic (A18-A21) and acidic (A22-A24) amino acids shows that the metal ion impregnated silica gel layers are more selective (strongly sorbing) for amino acids compared to unimpregnated silica gel layers. Conversely, plain silica gel layers are generally more selective for neutral amino acids (A1-A17) compared to impregnated layers as indicated by negative ΔR_F values for most of the amino acids. In cases of a few amino acids, the mobility remained unaltered by the impregnation and these amino acids show almost identical retention behavior on both the impregnated and unimpregnated silica gel layers ($\Delta R_F = \pm 0.05$). The change in selectivity of silica gel surface on impregnation with metal ions is probably brought about by the cation exchange reaction,

The silanol group ($-\text{SiOH}$) of the hydrated silica gel surface being weakly acidic undergoes cation exchange when silica gel is immersed in an aqueous salt solution⁹.

In addition to cations, the selectivity of silica gel is also altered by the impregnation with anions (Fig. 4). The negative ΔR_F value (R_F on plain silica gel $-R_F$ on anion impregnated silica gel) for most of the neutral amino acids (A1-

A17) is indicative that plain silica gel is more selective for neutral amino acids compared to impregnated silica gel layers. All basic amino acids (A18-A21) show higher selectivity (+ve ΔR_F value) towards impregnated silica gel layers compared to plain silica gel. In case of acidic amino acids (A22-A24), no significant effect of impregnation with Cl^- and I^- was observed on their mobility ($\Delta R_F \approx \pm 0.05$).

In view of spots compactness and the separation possibilities of amino acids on different stationary phases, 2% Cu-impregnated silica gel layers were found most suitable for tlc analysis of amino acids. As a result, selective separation of DL-phenylalanine from all other amino acids has been achieved. A few such separations are listed in Table 1. These separations are not possible if unimpregnated silica gel is used as adsorption medium. The separation of DL-alanine from DL-phenylalanine is of great importance from theoretical as well as practical point of view. It seems that the specific interaction of Cu^{2+} with phenyl group plays an important role in controlling the migration behavior of amino acids on Cu^{2+} -silica gel phase. The R_F value of each individual amino acid changes slightly when it is chromatographed in mixture with other amino acids.

Table 2 presents the detection and dilution limits of some amino acids. The proposed method is highly sensitive for the detection of amino acids at nanogram levels. L-Ornithine monohydrochloride at concentration level of 0.04 μg (or 40 ng) can be easily detected. Such a higher sensitivity is possible due to the presence of a water core in W/O microemulsion which is responsible for some sort of preconcentration of amino acids in restricted volume.

Experimental

A Toshniwal thin layer chromatographic apparatus with 20 \times 3 cm glass-plates and 24 \times 6 cm glass jars was used.

Alumina, silica gel G, microcrystalline cellulose, amino acids, heptane and inorganic salts (all C.D.H., India), pentanol (Fluka AG), sodium dodecyl sulphate (Qualigens, India) were used. All reagents were of AnalaR grade. Amino acids used were glycine (A1), L-hydroxyproline

(A2), DL-alanine (A3), DL-serine (A4), L-proline (A5), DL-valine (A6), DL-threonine (A7), L-cystiene hydrochloride (A8), L-leucine (A9), DL-isoleucine (A10), DL-nor-leucine (A11), DL-methionine (A12), L-tyrosine (A13), DL-tryptophan (A14), L-cystine (A15), DL-phenylalanine (A16), 3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl) (A17), L-ornithine monohydrochloride (A18), L-lysine monohydrochloride (A19), L-histadine monohydrochloride (A20), L-arginine monohydrochloride (A21), DL-aspartic acid (A22), L-glutamic acid (A23) and DL-2-amino-n-butyric acid (A24).

The test solutions (1%) of all amino acids were prepared in distilled water. A 0.4% ninhydrin solution in acetone was used to detect the amino acids. The appearance of dark violet spots showed the presence of amino acids.

The sorbents used as stationary phase were microcrystalline cellulose (S1), alumina (S2), silica gel G (S3) and silica gel G impregnated with 0.5–2% aqueous solution of metal ions (S4) (Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Fe^{III} and Cd^{II}) and anions (Cl^- , Br^- and I^-). The water-in-oil microemulsion used as mobile phase was prepared by titrating a coarse emulsion of n-heptane, deionized water and SDS with n-pentanol as reported earlier¹⁰. The microemulsion was produced at 30°.

Preparation of tlc plates : The plain silica gel plates were prepared as usual. Impregnated plate was prepared from the slurry by mixing silica gel, 0.5, 1.0 or 2% aqueous solution of copper sulphate, nickel chloride, cobalt nitrate, zinc nitrate, ferric chloride, cadmium chloride, mercuric chloride, sodium chloride, potassium iodide or ammonium bromide in 1 : 3 ratio by shaking for 5–10 min.

Procedure : An aliquot (10 μl) of test solution was spotted on a thin layer plate. The plates were developed in the chosen solvent system by the ascending technique. The solvent ascent was fixed to 10 cm in all cases. After development the plate was dried at room temperature, sprayed with freshly prepared ninhydrin solution and

heated at 90–100° for 15–20 min. The amino acids were detected as violet spots. The R_L (R_F of leading front) and R_T (R_F of trailing front) values for each spot were determined and the R_F value was calculated.

The limit of detection of various amino acids were determined by spotting different amounts of amino acids on the tlc plates, developing the plates and detecting the spots. The method was repeated with successive lowering of the amount of amino acids until no spots were detected. The lowest amount of amino acids detected on the tlc plates was taken as the limit of detection.

For the separation, equal amounts of amino acids to be separated were mixed and 10 μl of the resultant mixture was spotted on the tlc plate. The plate was developed, the spot⁸ detected and the R_F values of the separated amino acids were determined.

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